

The Black Hole and the Falling Star Hypothesis ***What If a Black Hole Is Just a Star Falling at the Speed of Light?***

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الثَّقْبُ الْأَسْوَدُ وَالنَّجْمُ الثَّاقِبُ

They have said much about it, so I do not tire of repeating what they said. They have described it with strange descriptions, so I will neither add nor subtract from that. I am not here to argue or refute, I am here to say what I have... and I do not quarrel. Others may blame me for my lack of capability and weak tools, I say: you have hit the bull's eye of truth... but I will not hold back. For I have a notion that has taken me in a different direction, and a thought that has inclined me towards a different path, so I walk forward... and I do not fear.

The black hole has long baffled reasoning minds and enlightened insights. It exists, evidenced by precise mathematical equations and data from highly efficient observation devices. Yet, despite that, it is absent from absolute certainty, attested by the multitude of conjectures and myths that orbit this miraculous entity. And all those hypotheses, without exception, deny that the mystery of the black hole is captive to the speed of its star, just as they deny the star's journey towards our Earth.

The Black Hole and The Fallen Star:

As for me, I say: The star was concealed from the earthly eye due to the speed of its fall towards it. The falling star preceded its image when its velocity reached or surpassed the speed of light. The eye did not perceive the falling star, but rather perceived its shadow. The universe behind it is luminous, while it is dark upon the eye; thus, the image of the star does not reach the eye, only the shadow arrives. And since this statement is difficult to comprehend, bitter for the mind, I present to you hereafter the proofs of my words, so do not rush.

Here are a series of questions that may captivate the mind and raise doubts about the credibility of the proposition. I pose them before you, attempting to answer them with what knowledge and intuition I possess.

The First Question: How can a celestial body reach the speed of light?

It was that Einstein who set a ceiling for the speed of matter, making it exclusive to light. He thus denied the right of others to attain that speed. As for me, I do not say his words, for my soul has long hated those ceilings, and I have often been overcome by the conviction that the universe abounds with what is far greater than that. I do not doubt for a moment that another entity has done it and does it constantly, surpassing that speed until light became, for it, among the category of the lazy and sluggish. For the universe continues to surprise us with amazing new things every day.

Science speaks of the hyper-rapid expansion of the universe, confirming that it far exceeds the speed of light. Then it rushes to justify the act by claiming that it is space that did it, and this does not contradict the law of relativity. And some in science speak of quantum entanglement, confirming the instantaneous communication between the two entangled parties. And while acknowledging this, it does not forget to deny that it violates Einstein's law and his relativity.

In this position, I am not dismantling a pillar of science, nor am I being arrogant towards a great science like Einstein's. I do not know the law of relativity, and I do not delve into its details and intricacies. Nevertheless, I do not deny myself the right to endorse another proposal that the mind finds tranquility and reassurance in. I do not fear any blame in that, for I have known blame since I was a child and an adolescent, and as an adult who grew weary of blame, so he turns away from it.

The Second Question: Then, how can we observe the star if its image is absent from us?

I say: by seeing its shadow. When a giant star falls towards Earth at a speed equal to or greater than the speed of light, the earthly observing eye cannot observe the star itself or its image. The image of the star merges with the star itself if its falling speed equals the speed of light, and it may lag behind it if it exceeds it in speed. All the

observing eye can do is observe the shadow of the star, not its image, thanks to the luminous background of the cosmic space. The eye sees a blackness it mistakes for the star itself, but the truth is that it is the star's shadow, not its image. And to simplify the matter for myself and for you, let us deconstruct the following three scenarios:

Scenario One: What happens if the star's falling speed is less than the speed of light?

In this case, the image of the star will reach the earthly observing eye much faster than the star itself, so the eye sees it as bright and shining. This hypothesis is not suitable to be a hypothesis for the black hole; see **Figure (1)**.

***Figure (1) The First Hypothesis:
The star's velocity is less than the speed of light***

Assume with me that the falling star is moving at a velocity less than that of light. In this case, its image will reach us very early. The light beam emitted from it will precede it by a great distance. This is self-evident and indisputable.

Important note:

For a more accurate understanding of the black hole and falling star hypothesis, watch the video at the following link:

Scenario Two: What is the situation if the star's falling speed equals the speed of light?

Here, the image of the star merges with the star itself, and they arrive together at the earthly observing eye, so no eye can ever observe the star. For when the star's image reaches Earth, it will find no eye to observe it, as the star itself has already crushed the Earth and all upon it.

*But before this, and at a very early stage, the observing eye can see the star's shadow, not its image. And the shadow, as we know it, is always black. Thus, we have laid the first hypothesis about the black hole; see **Figure (2)**.*

***Figure (2) The Second Hypothesis:
The star's falling speed equals the speed of light***

If the star's falling speed equals the speed of light, then the star will travel side-by-side with the light emitted from it, all along the path. Thus, the image of the falling star will coincide with its mass. An earthly eye – that is, at the other end where the point of impact is – will be unable to see the star except at the moment of collision. This is a consequence that is not favored. It is as if the image wears the essence and does not release it, making it impossible for the eye to see. The depth of the eye remains dark and gloomy, with no light to sweep away its desolation.

Important note:

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Scenario Three: Suppose the star's falling speed is greater than the speed of light, what happens?

Here, the image of the star lags behind the star itself, so no earthly eye can ever perceive the star. For the star itself crushes the Earth and all upon it at a time that precedes, by a lot or a little, the time of its image's arrival.

*As in the second hypothesis, the earthly eye can see only the star's shadow, and I say only, when the star passes in front of a luminous background of cosmic space; and this hypothesis is also suitable for explaining the black hole; see **Figure (3)**.*

***Figure (3) The Third Hypothesis:
The Star's Falling Speed is Greater Than the Speed of Light***

Let us assume that the speed of the falling star has surpassed the speed of light.

At that point, the star's essence becomes detached from its image.

The latter now chases frantically after the essence but is unable to catch up. Consequently, an earthly eye can never observe the star. By the time the image of the essence reaches Earth, it will find no one left to observe it.

Important note:

[For a more accurate understanding of the black hole and falling star hypothesis, watch the video at the following link:](#)

The Third Question: Hasn't the time come for this star to reach us, given it has reached the utmost speed?

I say, do not worry, it will inevitably reach us. It is the sudden event, so wait, I am with you among those who wait. The universe is vast, human minds have failed to comprehend its dimensions. Some stars are estimated to be millions of light-years away from Earth, and science continues to surprise us every day with what is even farther than that.. this is first. Secondly, the star falling towards us might change its course after a while, thus losing its property as a black hole, and also losing its danger to you and me.. so do not grieve.

The Fourth Question: Which is faster, light or shadow?

In this context, I will tell you what will be the evidence against me everywhere and always. But the soul incessantly whispers to me, and I cannot conceal the soul's whisper. The statement about the speed of the star's fall does not weigh, and will never weigh, what I will tell you about the properties of light and shadow. For my thought has taken me farther than refutative thought allows, and I say refutative, not critical, because it is the most appropriate description.

Much of science is based on the idea of the continuity of light, and consequently photons, even if the primary light source is obscured, temporarily or eternally. Therefore, science constantly tells us about the bygone past with images that have just reached us from deep space. This image tells of what was millions of years ago, and that is the state of the star before it vanished and disappeared from existence.. as they said and as they always say. As for me, I say the opposite, and my evidence for my saying is intuition and a mind that finds no rest.

Personally, I believe that the shadow is faster than light. I even go further to say that the shadow is instantaneous, and the light is hyper speed, and no matter how great speed becomes, it cannot approximate instantaneity in appearance. I also believe that light still hides its most important secrets from us. And I propose the hypothesis of

photon synergy and photon collapse. The continuity of the light source's appearance to its observer is the guarantee for the continuous flow of photons towards it. Sudden and instantaneous photon collapse occurs if the light source is obscured, either spontaneously or by an obstructing veil preventing that appearance. Thus, photon synergy and the continuity of light are contingent upon the permanence of the light source's appearance to its observer, and photon collapse is the result of the source being obscured from it. Thus also, the flow of photons, and with it light, consumes time, while the shadow is instantaneous, immeasurable in the calculation of time.

And since the image of a thing is nothing but light received by its observer, we do not see the image of the star falling towards us because its speed exceeded or equaled the speed of light. But we see its shadow because the star had obscured a part of the luminous background of the universe, for the shadow is instantaneous and preceded everything.

The Result:

In conclusion, I say: along its entire path or a segment of it, there is a giant star falling upon us, at a tremendous speed that exceeds or equals the value of the speed of light. The star's mass advanced ahead of its image, so the eye perceived it as blackness. And this is the habit of the eye, for it is not satisfied with anything but light as proof. The image of the star disappeared from us, but its shadow was present. So, the star appeared black like the kohl of the night, and around it, light seeped through from the luminous background of the universe. And thus, the shadow exists, and its luminous surroundings exist. Someone might say: Is this plausible? I say yes, and God Almighty has promised us that we will see His signs in the heavens and within ourselves.

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[To understand the hypothesis of the black hole and the falling star more accurately, watch the video at the following link:](#)

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